

SOME INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION ISSUES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH MEDIA LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This article reveals the intercultural problems of understanding the word combinations in Uzbek and English media communication language. The common phrases of interlingua communication are discussed from the point of view of lexicology. It manifests the concept of synonymic equivalence of cultural representations. In their turn, these word equivalences within a language can form the range of synonyms that are not included in dictionaries. As you know, the basis of any communication is a common or mutual code (shared code) among the participants in the communicative act. In the case of linguistic media communication, such a common code is the mutual understanding of linguistic units; without this, communication is impossible. In this regard, the issues of equivalence become especially acute since it is the concept of equivalence in all aspects (semantics and especially different types of connotations) that determines the degree of public understanding in media communication.

Difficulties that arise in interlingua communication can be both explicit

(volume of meaning, differences in speech usage, stylistic connotations) and implicit, hidden and therefore more dangerous in media communication.

Hereby, we consider two main implicit reasons that complicate communication in general and in particular for non-native speakers.

1. Collocations, or phraseological lexical units, are restrictions governing the use of the language. This means that each word in a language has its own range of compatibility that is unique to that language. In other words, it combines with some words and makes collocations or phrases with them, but it cannot make these constructions with all the words of the language. Why can we only use the word *galaba* with *qozonmoq* (to win a victory) and *maglubiyatga uchramoq* (to suffer a defeat), or *rol* with *oynamoq* (to play a role), *ahamiyatga ega bolmoq* (to have significance), and *xulosa yoki qoshimcha qilmoq* (to draw conclusions and make compliments)

There are a number of words that are combined with the lexis that do not often occur in the same context of concept: For example, the English verb to pay, which means to give (someone) money that is due for work done, goods received, or a debt incurred, or to suffer a misfortune as a result of an action, is supposed to be combined with such incompatible words as attention [*diqqar*], visit [*tashrif*], and compliments [*maqtoʻv, xushomad*] in the Uzbek language. Otherwise, the Uzbek word combinations *balandparvoz soʻz* (=high-flying words), *acchiq choy* (=bitter tea), and *kuchli yomgir* (=strong rain) sound like arrogant words, strong tea, and heavy rain in English.

A word in a language has its own lexical and phraseological compatibility, or valence. It is national (and not universal) in the sense that it is inherent only in this particular word in this particular language. This specificity becomes apparent only when comparing languages, just as a native culture is revealed in a collision with a foreign one. Therefore, native speakers do not see these main

difficulties for a foreign language learner: it never occurs to them that tea can be strong in some languages, and compliments may be used with the word to make.

That is why, when studying a foreign language, we need to memorise words not separately, according to their meanings, but in the natural, most stable combinations inherent in this language.

Lexical compatibility complicates the concept of equivalence and undermines the foundations of translation. Bilingual dictionaries confirm this phenomenon. The translation of words with the help of a dictionary, which gives the "equivalents" of their meanings in another language, confuses students, provoking them to use foreign words in the usual contexts of their native language while these contexts coincide very rarely. Xalqaro aloqalar-international relations, Xalqaro miqiyos-global sphere

Let's consider the word "book" in terms of prevalence and its equivalent, the word "kitob" in Uzbek. In the English-Uzbek dictionary, this word is given in the most regularly reproduced combinations. Only one of them is translated by the word "book." a ~ on/about birds – qushlar hayoti haqidagi kitob,

a reference book –katalog,

a cheque book – chek daftarchasi,

a ration book – kartochnka,

to do the books – hisob yuritmoq,

our order books are full – biz boshqa buyurtma olmaymiz,

to be in smb's bad books – kimning qora royxatida bolmoq,

I can read her like a book – men uni juda yaxshi bilaman,

we must stick to/go by the book – a reference book –katalog,

a cheque book – chek daftarchasi,

a ration book – kartochnka,

To do the books—hisob Yuritmoq,

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to be in SMB's bad books – kimning qora royxatida bolmoq,

I can read her like a book – men uni juda yaxshi bilaman,

We must stick to/go by the book – qoidalarga qattiq amal qilishimiz kerak,

I'll take a leaf out of your book—men sendan ornak olaman,

He was brought to book for that – buning uchun uni soroqqa tutdilar

The same situation—when the translation of a single word does not match the translations of this word in phrases—can be illustrated with examples from the Uzbek-English dictionary:

Eslatma- note, Konspekt olish – note-taking; biznes xat – memorandum, hisobot xati – report; sevgi maktubi - love letter, ishqiy noma- billet–doux; yopiq – closed, yopiq majlis - private meeting, yopiq(yashirin) ovoz berish - secret ballot, yopiq inshoot - indoors (PACC).

At the level of word-combination, these differences are even more striking. On occasion, one can shock the audience with the assertion that people who speak Uzbek use the phrase boshini yuvmoq (wash one's head), which can be translated into English to wash one's hair, as their language suggests. And the Uzbek people don't really mean to wash their heads with shampoo and water, as it literally means. They are strange people! They wash their hair because the equivalent of the Uzbek phrase 'boshini yuvmoq' (to wash one's head) is the English phrase "to wash one's hair". It is surprising that with such a development of "social correctness" of this phrase, no one has so far been ashamed of offending bald people who also have to say "my hair" in English, although how much more natural it would be for them in Uzbek to wash their heads. Everyone has a head, but not all have hair... As for the expression to

wash one's head in English, it is used in a figurative sense, close to the Uzbek phrase, also with an impolite figurative meaning, to lather your neck.

2. Another difficulty, even more hidden than the secrets and unpredictability of lexical and phraseological compatibility, is the conflict between the cultural ideas of different peoples about those objects and phenomena of reality that are indicated by the "equivalent" words of these languages. These cultural representations usually determine the appearance of different stylistic connotations of words in different languages.

So, even the designation of green color, such a "universal" concept, raises great doubts in terms of its absolute lexical correspondence, since the presence of certain metaphorical and stylistic connotations cannot but affect the meaning of the word, and these connotations are different in different languages. Green eyes in Russian sound poetic, romantic, suggestive of magic, reminding me of the eyes of a mermaid.

While in the English phrase, "green eyes" is a metaphor for envy and contains clear negative connotations. The negative associations caused by the phrase "green eyes" are Shakespeare's "fault", who called envy in the tragedy "Othello" a "green-eyed monster"—the jealousy that threatens to eat him up and drive him mad if he allows it to do so.

That layer of vocabulary that combines "equivalent" words presents much greater difficulties in learning a foreign language than a non-equivalent or not fully equivalent part of the dictionary. The fact is that the apparent conceptual equivalence, or rather the equivalence of reality, misleads the student, and he can use the word without taking into account the peculiarities of the linguistic functioning of this word in someone else's speech, its phraseological compatibility, and lingual-stylistic connotations. In other words, in those

seemingly simple cases when the words of different languages include the same amount of conceptual material and reflect the same piece of reality, their actual use of speech may be different since it is determined by different linguistic thinking and different speech functioning.

So, linguistic equivalence is a myth that crumbles if we take into account such factors as the volume of semantics, stylistic connotations, and lexical compatibility. All linguists, translators, and teachers of foreign languages are familiar with these problems. The cultural-linguistic aspect of the equivalence of words in different languages received much less attention and therefore turned out to be much more hidden, deeper, and less studied.

The meaning of the word as a language unit is correlated with a certain object or phenomenon in the real world. However, not only can these objects or phenomena be completely different in different cultures (e.g., the houses of an Eskimo, a Chinese, a Kyrgyz and an Englishman are very different houses). It is important that cultural concepts about these objects and phenomena will also be different since they live and function in different modern worlds and cultures.

We can conclude the point that, behind linguistic equivalence, lies conceptual equivalence and equivalence of cultural representations. In their turn, these word equivalences within a language can form the range of words that have similar meanings in certain languages.

Reference

Тер-Минасова С. Г. Язык и межкультурная коммуникация. Москва 2000

Верецагин Е. М., Костомаров В. Г.. Язык и культура. М., 1990, с. 51.

Виноградов В. С.. Лексические вопросы перевода художественной прозы. М., 1978, с. 56.

A. Mazrui. The Political Sociology of the English Language. Mouton - the

Hague, 1975, p. 81

